

SEISMEC

NEWSWAVE

Dear reader,

Welcome to our 2nd official newsletter! We are excited to bring you the latest updates and insights from the [SEISMEC](#) project.

In this second issue, we delve into SEISMEC's work packages that drive our mission for human-centric innovation, reflect on valuable outcomes from our General Assembly in Berlin, proudly present our participation in major events, reflect on our first-year activities and give you a glimpse of what is coming next.

Jump in, fasten your seatbelt and get ready to pilot the shift towards a human-centric industry!

The graphic features the text 'SEISMEC core ideas' centered on a background of white, 3D-rendered geometric shapes that resemble a cracked or shattered surface. The word 'SEISMEC' is in a large, bold, sans-serif font, with 'SEIS' in green and 'MEC' in blue. Below it, 'core' and 'ideas' are stacked vertically in a smaller, bold, blue sans-serif font.

SEISMEC

core ideas

Building Human-Centric Innovation: Unfolding SEISMEC's core ideas.

SEISMEC is dedicated to boosting European industrial competitiveness by focusing on human-centric solutions. This four-year project encompasses several key work packages (WPs), each aimed at fostering innovation that prioritises worker empowerment and well-being. WP1 sets the theoretical foundation, ensuring technologies align with human values. **WP2 and WP3** bridge theory to practice, creating tools and piloting solutions in real workplaces. **WP4 and WP5** analyse pilot outcomes to enhance productivity and competitiveness, while **WP6** focuses on outreach, building a sustainable ecosystem for long-term impact. SEISMEC's journey reflects a collaborative approach to a responsible industrial future.

[DIVE DEEPER HERE](#)

PROSPECTS 5.0 & SEISMEC EU projects are joining forces!

PROSPECTS^{5.0}

PROGRESS
TOWARDS
INDUSTRY 5.0

Let us introduce you to [PROSPECTS 5.0](#). Our first project collaboration! The PROSPECTS 5.0 project explores Industry 5.0 adoption by analysing 14 real-world use-cases across sectors like manufacturing, IT services, education, energy, aviation, and automotive in the European Union, Norway, and Türkiye. The project conducts various studies and activities aimed on providing the practical guidance, tools, and solutions for industry stakeholders to remove the barriers for industry to opt into the Industry 5.0 shift.

[Learn more about the project and its use-cases](#)

Recent updates from the PROSPECTS 5.0:

The Industry 5.0 Community Trends and Status Report synthesizes insights from 879 studies, providing a broad analysis of existing models to identify sectoral commonalities, methodological gaps, and emerging trends. Building on this foundation, a multi-round Delphi survey involving 14 experts from diverse EU countries was conducted. This iterative consultation process ensured the integration of regional and contextual perspectives, capturing both technological and non-technological drivers of Industry 5.0 adoption.

[Read full article and report here](#)

Industry 5.0 Wiki, one of the most comprehensive platforms in Europe dedicated to advancing knowledge and collaboration around Industry 5.0 principles, is planned to be launched on 9th of January 2025. This platform showcases valuable knowledge in the form of articles, videos, and podcasts, initiative and resources, standardization and regulatory information, industry-specific insights and much more. Everyone interested in or experienced with Industry 5.0 are invited to contribute to this collaborative database.

[LEARN MORE](#)

Highlights from SEISMEC's General Assembly in Berlin

At SEISMEC's General Assembly in Berlin, partners made significant progress in preparing for the project's pilot implementations. Key discussions focused on aligning timelines, defining KPIs, and advancing human-centric goals through workshops on data management, ethics, and explainable AI. Interactive sessions and cross-sectoral insights highlighted the importance of collaboration, transparency, and user trust and ensuring impactful, human-centric innovation.

[READ OUR STORY](#)

SEISMEC turns 1!

Time has flown, and just like that, we've wrapped up the first 12 months of SEISMEC's implementation journey! In its first year, SEISMEC has redefined the industrial landscape with a bold, human-centric approach. Building on the benchmarking of practices and guidelines for human-centrism the project established a solid foundation for the [SEISMEC framework](#). This groundwork supported the development of human-centric tools and methods, shaping the goals and activities of the pilots and enabling the launch of 17 pilots across 14 countries.

[EXPLORE OUR JOURNEY](#)

SEISMEC in Action: Engaging at 24 events!

Over 2024, SEISMEC made its mark at 24 events, from major conferences to interactive workshops. Highlights included showcasing human-centric innovations at the [Innohealth Forum 2024](#), "Health Tech for Humanity" and the [Industry 5.0 plenary](#), with impactful discussions on the future of work and AI.

[LEARN MORE](#)

SEISMEC Reading corner

Keep up to date with the latest SEISMEC articles, where we explore project milestones as well as news related to Industry 5.0. From pilot project summaries to reflections on industry workshops, our blog keeps you connected to the latest innovations and insights guiding SEISMEC's impact on European industries.

[READ MORE](#)

*The SEISMEC project is leaving behind 2024 having created the best memories and looks forward with excitement to pursuing its goals in the coming year! The SEISMEC consortium is wishing you a season filled with love, joy, and warmth. **Happy Holidays!***

Funded by the
European Union

SEISMEC © 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101135884. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.